

Comment on "Elastic Tensors from Pairwise Energy Frameworks in Molecular Crystals"

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Abstract

Recently, a simple approximation compatible with any method to predict intermolecular interaction energies was proposed by Blake I. Armstrong and Peter R. Spackman in [JCTC]. The equilibrium pair model (EPM) was developed to directly and efficiently yield an estimate of the complete elasticity tensor. Unfortunately, the paper contains some fairly basic errors in continuum mechanics and computational nanomechanics.

In their latest publication,¹ Blake I. Armstrong and Peter R. Spackman proposed a simple approximation, the Equilibrium Pairwise Model (EPM), compatible with any method to predict intermolecular interaction energies, that directly and efficiently yields an estimate of the complete elasticity tensor. They claim to have proposed a protocol applicable to any molecular crystal structure. Unfortunately, the paper contains some fairly basic flaws in the fields of continuum mechanics and computational nanomechanics.

- Ibid.[S2.6, P.S-16] is written: "*The deformation was applied through the transformation: $\mathbf{F} = (\mathbf{I} + \varepsilon)$ where \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient and ε is the strain tensor.*"

A valid expression would be:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = \frac{\partial(\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{u})}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = (\mathbf{I} - \nabla \mathbf{u}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor, \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient tensor, and $\nabla \mathbf{u}$ is the displacement gradient tensor.² Both are generally non-symmetric and have nine independent components. In brief, the deformation gradient, \mathbf{F} is a linear operator describing local stretch and rotation of a material neighborhood: $d\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{F}d\mathbf{X}$. In nanomechanics, we use this transformation as the basis for the so-called *Cauchy-Born* rule.² Since pure rotations do not contribute to the deformation of a body, deformation measures that are independent of rotation are introduced, such as the right Cauchy–Green deformation tensor: $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}$. Since $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{I}$ for an undeformed body and we are interested in the differences between configurations, i.e., relative deformations, we introduce the concept of strain, where the fundamental tensor is the Lagrangian finite strain tensor, also called the Green strain tensor defined as

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I}) = \frac{1}{2}[\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T] + \frac{1}{2}[(\nabla \mathbf{u})^T \nabla \mathbf{u}], \quad (2)$$

and then linearization of the Green strain tensor yields the infinitesimal strain tensor, also called linear strain tensor, or small strain tensor

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}[\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T] = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{F} - 2\mathbf{I}). \quad (3)$$

Although both tensors, \mathbf{E} and ε , are symmetric, the small strain tensor is not objective and does not vanish under rigid rotations, as this can generate spurious stresses and energy.³In fact, there is no reason to use the small-strain tensor when calculating the elas-

ticity tensor in nanomechanics if the stress-strain or energy-strain method is employed, as it does not make the process easier. One should simply keep in mind that both DFT and molecular statics yield the Cauchy stress tensor, but the Green–Lagrange finite strain tensor is energy conjugate to the second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor.

- Ibid.[P.3] appears: "*uniaxial pressure*"

In fact, there is no such thing as uniaxial pressure; there can be uniaxial stress. Pressure is a scalar and in continuum mechanics is defined as $p = -\frac{1}{3}\text{Tr}\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. If the stress is not uniform in all directions ($\sigma_{11} \neq \sigma_{22} \neq \sigma_{33} \neq \sigma_{11}$), the pressure is non-hydrostatic or non-isotropic and is expressed as the mean normal stress.

- Ibid.[P.4] is written: "... as a function of strain via central finite differences with an applied strain of 0.1."

When determining the stiffness tensor using the stress-strain or energy-strain methods, the magnitude of the perturbation must satisfy two requirements. First, it must be small enough that the finite differences provide a good approximation of the true derivative. Second, it must fall within the elastic range of the structure being analyzed. The strain of 0.1, i.e., 10%, certainly does not meet the first requirement and most likely does not meet the second one either. It is difficult to consider the Authors' findings reliable. In the well-known DFT results database, Materials Project,^{4,5} the default maximum perturbation is 1%.

- Ibid.[P.4,5] is written: "*Machine-Learned Interatomic Potentials ... Elastic tensors were computed via finite differences using systematic cell deformations ($\pm 2\%$ strain) with subsequent atomic relaxation, without imposing symmetry constraints.*"

In the widely recognized LAMMPS Molecular Dynamics Simulator,⁶ the default strain magnitude is set to 10^{-6} , i.e., 0.0001%, in the examples/ELASTIC.

- Ibid.[P.10] is written: "*When comparing elastic tensors between methods or against experiment the orientation of the Cartesian reference frame is fundamentally important, yet frequently overlooked.*"

To avoid problems with stiffness tensors from different reference frames, one can, e.g., use Kelvin moduli, which are invariants of the stiffness tensor and do not depend on the orientation of the Cartesian basis.⁷

- Ibid.[P.1] in the title and several times in the text appears: "*Elastic Tensors*"

It has become established that there are elastic constants, but rather an elasticity and stiffness tensor. This mistake appears quite often in physics and chemistry publications and computer programs, but that doesn't change the fact that it is a mistake.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the National Science Centre (NCN – Poland) Research Project: No. 2021/43/B/ST8/03207.

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TOC Graphic

$$\mathbf{F} = (\mathbf{I} + \nabla \mathbf{u}) \neq (\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$$
$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} [\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T]$$